

SpaceTeamSat1
Preliminary Requirements Document
Electric Power System

03.04.2023

Version 1.2

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author(s)	Description
0.1	15.12.2021	David Freismuth	First Review
1.0	15.01.2022	David Freismuth	Implemented feedback from review; Release
1.1	14.04.2022	David Freismuth	Added requirement 9-EPS-1 in response to the addition of system requirement 9. Changed requirements 1-EPS-9 and 2-EPS-1, 4-EPS-1. ID 1-EPS-18 has been assigned two times. The requirement with the title “Extendable Solar Cells” has now the ID 1-EPS-19.
1.2	03.04.2023	David Freismuth, Patrick Kappl	Added requirement 1-EPS-20, 1-EPS-21 and 1-EPS-22; Updated power budget and 9-EPS-1; New title page; Improved citations;

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Glossary

- CDS** CubeSat Design Specification; Document that holds the specification for CubeSats. 16
- CSBI** CubeSat Bus Interface; The Bus which is used on SpaceTeamSat 1 (STS1) for communication between the subsystems. 5–10, 17
- CubeSat** A satellite, that adheres to the CubeSat design specification. 1, 2, 12–15, 17, 18
- DOD** Depth of discharge; A parameter of a battery, that describes how much of its nominal capacity can be discharged without damaging the battery. 8, 16
- EPS** Electric Power System; The subsystem of a CubeSat, that provides and conditions electric energy. 2–6, 8–10, 13–15, 17
- ESA** European Space Agency; An intergovernmental organisation of 22 member states dedicated to the exploration of space. 1, 3
- FYS** Fly-Your-Satellite; An European Space Agency (ESA) programm, that sponsors CubeSat missions with academic goals. 2, 3
- NASA** National Aeronautics and Space Administration; An independent agency of the U.S. federal government responsible for the civilian space program, as well as aeronautics and space research. 14
- PCB** Printed Circuit Board; Board that mounts electronics and the electric connections between them. 5, 6, 10–13
- PDR** Preliminary Design Review; A technical review, where the preliminary requirements are evaluated and locked in. Furthermore, design choices, that have been made until this point shall be challenged. 2
- RBF** Remove Before Flight pin; A pin that is inserted into the CubeSat. While it is inserted, most CubeSat functions are disabled.. 14–16
- STS1** SpaceTeamSat 1; The name of the first CubeSat mission of the TU Wien SpaceTeam (TUST) and the corresponding satellite. 1–3
- TID** Total ionizing dose; A measure for the accumulated exposition to radiation. 13
- TUST** TU Wien SpaceTeam, The team behind STS1. 1
- UCI** Umbilical Cord Interface; External connector on the CubeSat, that is specified by the CubeSat specification. 13

1. Introduction

This document serves as the preliminary requirements document of the Electric Power System (EPS) submodule of the STS1 CubeSat. It defines the requirements to the EPS and therefore the minimum performance of the future submodule. As this document is fabricated at an early project phase, requirements may be subject to change, until they are reviewed and locked in at a future Preliminary Design Review (PDR).

The EPS is the subsystem that provides the electrical energy that is necessary to power all other CubeSat subsystems. The EPS includes solar cells, batteries, voltage transformation circuits and security circuits.

1.1. Related Documents

This document relates to the following other publications. They may be referenced by the given short sign or the respective number throughout the document.

Short Sign	Document Name	Purpose
STS1PDR,[1]	SpaceTeamSat1 Preliminary Design Document: System Architecture	Describes the system architecture
STS1DATA,[2]	SpaceTeamSat1 Dataflow Game Document	Describes the data flow on STS1
FYSD,[3]	Fly Your Satellite! Design Specification Version 3.0	Describes requirements of CubeSats that participate in the FYS program.
CDS,[4]	CubeSat Design Specification Rev.12	Specifies the CubeSats standard.
JX	JAXA JEM Payload Accommodation Handbook	Specifies requirements to payloads.
NS	NASA Crewed Space Vehicle Battery Safety Requirements	States requirements to on-board batteries.
NR	NanoRacks CubeSat Deployer Interface Control Document	Specifies a CubeSat deployment system.

2. Requirements

All requirements shall be correct, unambiguous, traceable, measurable and verifiable. Furthermore, requirements shall answer the “Why?” by specifying the “What?” and not addressing the “How?”. For nomenclature reasons, we use the same wording to formulate requirements as in the FYS design specification [5] by the ESA:

- The word “shall” is used to express requirements that have to be met.
- The word “should” is used to express recommendations.
- The word “may” is used to express permissions.

Requirements are listed in the following format:

ID	X-Subsystem-Y
Title	Example Requirement
Text	This is the text of an example requirement.
Notes	This is a note to a requirement.

ID Unambiguous ID of the requirement. The id follows the format <Source>-<Subsystem>-<Number>. For instance, an ID of a requirement that originates from system requirement 1 and belongs to the EPS subsystem, may be “1-EPS-2”.

Title A short name of the requirement.

Text The content of the requirement.

Notes Additional information to the requirement. Notes do not have binding character, but may give more insight why this requirement exists or where it originates from.

2.1. System Requirements

System Requirements are high-level requirements that the system as whole shall be able to fulfill. From them, lower level requirements are derived. Lower level requirements shall always state, which system requirement they intend to support. The system requirements for the STS1 mission have been defined in [1]. For clearness reasons, they shall be repeated here:

- 1 The CubeSat shall have a system to generate power and distribute it to all other subsystems.

Note:

It shall be possible that the CubeSat can be powered solely by the solar cells, solely by the batteries, respectively both. The power distribution is only active in the operation phase of the CubeSat mission.

- 2 The CubeSat shall automatically charge the batteries as long as there is excess energy available.
Note:
Excess energy is the difference between the power provided by the solar cells and the power needed to power the subsystems of the CubeSat.
- 3 The CubeSat shall automatically transmit a beacon at least once every minute.
Note:
Obviously, this can only be done if enough power is provided.
- 4 The CubeSat shall be able to receive commands, when not transmitting data.
Note:
The CubeSat shall portion large amounts of data before transmission. After a certain amount of transmitted data the CubeSat has a transmission dead-time, which can be used to receive commands.
- 5 The CubeSat shall be able to deactivate all systems not necessary for communication once a corresponding command is received.
Note:
Relevant subsystems for communication are the EPS and the COBC.
- 6 The CubeSat shall operate according to a pre-defined state-chart.
Note:
Note that special attention needs to be paid for the launch phase.
- 7 The CubeSat shall have a single master, which is located on the COBC.
Note:
The master is the only subsystem that is able to initiate active communication with other subsystems on the CubeSat platform.
- 8 The primary ground station shall be able to send data and commands to the CubeSat. The primary ground station shall also be able to receive data from the CubeSat.
Note:
The communication capabilities shall be verified by a HAF, where the CubeSat shall be placed, for example, in an airplane or a hot air balloon. Additional GS' should be able to receive data from the CubeSat.
- 9 The EDU module shall be operable for at least 10% of the mission duration. The maximum continuous up time of the EDU shall be at least 3 h.

2.2. EPS Requirements

ID	1-EPS-1
Title	Number of Solar Cells
Text	The EPS shall provide the possibility to harvest energy from 8 solar cells. The EPS shall be able to operate with any number of connected solar cells from 1 to up to 8.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-2
Title	EPS Polarity
Text	Solar cells that are connected with inversed polarity, shall not interfere with the functionality of the rest of the EPS.
Notes	The main cause for this requirement is to protect the EPS from accidental wrong connection of the solar cells. If a charged battery is connected to the EPS, it may discharge over an inversed connected solar cell, which may lead to the destruction of EPS components.

ID	1-EPS-3
Title	Solar Cells Polarity
Text	Inverse connection of the solar cell shall not lead to destruction of the solar cell.
Notes	The main cause for this requirement is to protect solar cells from accidental wrong connections. If a charged battery is connected to the EPS, it may discharge over an inversed connected solar cell, which may lead to the destruction of the solar cell.

ID	1-EPS-4
Title	Solar Cell Voltage
Text	The EPS shall be able to accept solar cells with maximum voltages of 1 V to 3 V.
Notes	The flight model will most likely be fitted with triple junction solar cells. Such cells most often output 2.5 V. In order to be able to test with commercially available single junction cells (which are much more affordable), the EPS shall be compatible with cells that supply down to 1 V.

ID	1-EPS-5
Title	EPS Independence
Text	The EPS shall operate independently from any other subsystem. Other subsystems shall not be able make any changes to the behaviour of the EPS. Excluded from this requirement is the housekeeping data interface.
Notes	The housekeeping data interface is excluded from the independence of the EPS, since the sensors connected to the housekeeping data interface may have to be configured. Other subsystems are responsible for this configuration.

ID	1-EPS-6
Title	Housekeeping Data Interface Permissions
Text	Via the housekeeping data interface, the following actions are permitted to other subsystems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Configuration of sensors that are attached to the interface 2. Readout of sensor data All other actions are not allowed.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-7
Title	PCB Outline
Text	The PCBs of the EPS shall fit within the outline specified by fig. 2.1. The EPS may consist of up to four of such PCBs. These PCBs shall be stacked together along the z-axis via the CSBI.
Notes	-

Figure 2.1.: The outline of the EPS PCB.

ID	1-EPS-8
Title	Bus Connector
Text	The EPS PCB shall implement a CSBI. The CSBI consists of two samtec ESQT-125-03-M-D-309[6] board connectors, placed at the positions specified in Figure 2.2. The pin definition is specified by Table 2.10 and Table 2.11.
Notes	Each of the connectors consists of two columns of pins. They are shorted row-wise for redundancy and a higher current capability. This effectively turn the 50 pins connector into a 25 pin one.

Pin Header X-		
	Pin Function	Used in Subsystem
1	2 GND	
3	4 GND	
5	6 VBUS	EPS, COBC, EDU
7	8 VBUS	EPS, COBC, EDU
9	10 GND	
11	12 SPARE_1	
13	14 EDU_HEARTBEAT	COBC, EDU
15	16 UART_COBC_EDU_TX	COBC, EDU
17	18 UART_COBC_EDU_RX	COBC, EDU
19	20 GND	
21	22 EDU_EN	COBC, EDU
23	24 EDU_UPDATE	COBC, EDU
25	26 GND	
27	28 EDU_SPI_CLK	EPS, EDU
29	30 EDU_SPI_MOSI	EPS, EDU
31	32 EDU_SPI_MISO	EPS, EDU
33	34 EDU_SPI_CS1	EPS, EDU
35	36 EDU_SPI_CS2	EPS, EDU
37	38 EDU_SPI_CS3	EPS, EDU
39	40 GND	
41	42 SPARE_2	
43	44 SPARE_3	
45	46 SPARE_4	
47	48 GND	
49	50 GND	

Table 2.10.: The definition of the CSBI header in X- direction.

Pin Header X+		
	Pin Function	Used in Subsystem
1	2	GND
3	4	GND
5	6	EPS_BAT_FAULT
7	8	SPARE_6
9	10	SPARE_7
11	12	SPARE_8
13	14	UCI_COBC_UART_TX EPS, COBC
15	16	UCI_COBC_UART_RX EPS, COBC
17	18	UCI_COBC_3V3 EPS, COBC
19	20	GND
21	22	EPS_BAT_GOOD
23	24	EPS_ANT_DEPLOY EPS, COBC
25	26	EPS_CHARGING EPS, COBC
27	28	GND EPS, COBC
29	30	COBC_SPI_CLK EPS,COBC
31	32	COBC_SPI_MOSI EPS, COBC
33	34	COBC_SPI_MISO EPS, COBC
35	36	COBC_SPI_CS1 EPS, COBC
37	38	COBC_SPI_CS2 EPS, COBC
39	40	COBC_SPI_CS3 EPS, COBC
41	42	GND
43	44	VBUS
45	46	VBUS
47	48	GND
49	50	GND

Table 2.11.: The definition of the CSBI header in X+ direction.

ID	1.3.EPS.9
Title	Output Voltage
Text	The output voltage of the EPS shall be within the range of 5V and 8.4V. It shall be supplied to the VBUS pins of the CSBI. The ground reference shall be connected to the GND pins of the CSBI.
Notes	-

ID	1.4.EPS.10
Title	Output Ripple Voltage
Text	The output voltage ripple at CSBI pin VBUS shall be less than 100 mV.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-11
Title	Output Power
Text	As long as the battery is within its DOD specification, the EPS shall be able to supply 20 W of power at CSBI pin VBUS.
Notes	-

Figure 2.2.: The dimensions and location of the system bus connector on the EPS PCB.

ID	1-EPS-12
Title	Battery Good Indicator
Text	The CSBI pin EPS_BAT_GOOD shall be pulled high by the EPS, if the EPS' battery has more than 75% remaining capacity left. In all other cases, this pin shall be pulled low by the EPS. The remaining capacity shall be defined via the voltage of the battery.
Notes	This signal may be used by the COBC, to determine when to turn on the EDU.

ID	1-EPS-13
Title	Battery Charge Indicator
Text	If the EPS' battery is charging, the CSBI pin EPS_CHARGING shall be pulled high by the EPS. In all other cases, the pin shall be pulled low by the EPS.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-14
Title	Battery Fault Indicator
Text	If the EPS' battery is below 10% remaining capacity or if no battery is connected to the EPS or if the EPSs battery terminals are shorted, the CSBI pin EPS_BAT_FAULT shall be pulled high by the EPS. In all other cases, the pin shall be pulled low by the EPS. The remaining capacity shall be defined via the battery voltage.
Notes	This signal may be used by the COBC, to determine when to shut off the EDU.

ID	1-EPS-15
Title	Antenna Deployment Indicator
Text	If the CSBI pin EPS_ANT_DEPLOY is driven high by another subsystem, the EPS shall enable a high current path that leads to the antenna release mechanism. This path shall be able to carry a current of 3 A. If EPS_ANT_DEPLOY is pulled low, this path shall be disabled.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-16
Title	Solar Cell Area X+
Text	The solar panel PCB on the X+ face shall have the outline specified by fig. 2.3. Solar Cells shall not protrude over non-hatched areas.
Notes	-

Figure 2.3.: The outline of the solar panel PCB in X+ direction.

ID	1-EPS-17
Title	Solar Panel X-
Text	The solar panel PCB on the X- face shall have the outline specified by fig. 2.4. Solar Cells shall not protrude over non-hatched areas.
Notes	-

Figure 2.4.: The outline of the solar panel PCB in X- direction.

ID	1-EPS-18
Title	Solar Panel Y
Text	The solar panel PCBs on the Y- and Y+ faces shall have the outline specified by fig. 2.5. Solar Cells shall not protrude over non-hatched areas.
Notes	-

Figure 2.5.: The outline of the solar panel PCB in Y+ and Y- direction.

ID	1-EPS-19
Title	Extendable Solar Cells
Text	The CubeSat shall not implement extendable solar panels.
Notes	-

ID	1-EPS-20
Title	Solar Panel Z+
Text	The solar panel PCBs on the Z+ face shall have the outline specified by fig. 2.6. Solar Cells shall not protrude over non-hatched areas.
Notes	-

Figure 2.6.: The outline of the solar panel PCB in Z+ direction.

ID	1-EPS-21
Title	Temperature Range
Text	The EPS shall be operable within the temperature range of -15°C – 60°C .
Notes	This also complies with FYS 2.7.3.1.

ID	1-EPS-22
Title	Radiation Tolerance
Text	The EPS shall be operable up to a TID of 100 krad.
Notes	-

ID	FYS-EPS-1
Title	External Charger
Text	The battery pack integrated into the EPS shall be chargeable via an external charger, without the necessity of disassembling the CubeSat. The charging port shall be accessible via the UCI.
Notes	-

ID	FYS-EPS-2
Title	External Charger Independence
Text	It shall not be possible to power other subsystems via the external charger.
Notes	This requirement originates from NR 4.2.1.4 and FYS 2.2.1.4.

ID	FYS-EPS-3
Title	Deployment Timer
Text	The EPS shall implement a timer that expires after (45 ± 1) min. This timer shall be started after the CubeSat is ejected of the launch vehicle (i.e. all deployment switches are no longer actuated and the RBF pin has been removed). Only after expiration of this timer, other CubeSat systems shall be supplied with voltage. Before its first expiration, the timer shall be reset, when the the RBF pin is inserted, or one or more deployment switches are actuated. After its first expiration, the timer function shall be deactivated indefinitely. I.e. other subsystems shall be immediately supplied with power.
Notes	This requirement originates from FYS 2.2.2.5 and 2.2.6.2.

ID	FYS-EPS-4
Title	Battery Protection
Text	The battery pack of the EPS shall be protected by an overcharging- and over discharging protection function.
Notes	This requirement originates from the FYS requirement FYS 2.2.1.1

ID	FYS-EPS-5
Title	Battery Compliance
Text	The EPS batteries shall be compliant to NASA crewed space vehicle battery safety requirements JSC 20793 (RD6).
Notes	This requirement originates from NR 4.4.7 and FYS 2.2.1.3.

ID	FYS-EPS-6
Title	Battery Short Protection
Text	The EPS batteries shall provide safety features at cell level to prevent damage by internal and external short circuits
Notes	This requirement originates from NR 4.4.7.4, 4.4.7.5 and FYS 2.2.1.5.

ID	FYS-EPS-7
Title	Pouch Battery Pressure Release
Text	In case the EPS implements pouch cells, these cells shall have pressure restraints on the wide faces of the cells, in order to prevent swelling in vacuum.
Notes	This requirement originates from NR 4.4.7.9 and FYS 2.2.1.7.

ID	FYS-EPS-8
Title	Internal Batteries
Text	Energy storage devices shall not be placed on the outside of the satellite.
Notes	This requirement originates from NR 4.2.1.1 and FYS 2.2.1.9.

ID	FYS-EPS-9
Title	Battery Cable Length
Text	Between the energy storage device and the first electrical inhibit shall be no more than 152 mm of 26AWG wire.
Notes	If more than 152 mm of wire is required between the batteries and the first electrical inhibit, then SAE AS22759-compliant wiring, or equivalent, shall be utilised. Furthermore, the wire shall be insulated with PTFE or ETFE and shall be heat-resistant up to 200 °C. This requirement originates from NR 4.2.1.7 and FYS 2.2.1.10.

ID	FYS-EPS-10
Title	Deployment Switches
Text	<p>The EPS shall implement at least four deployment switches, which prevent the activation of the satellite, while the satellite is inserted in the launch device. While at least one deployment switch is actuated, the CubeSat shall be deactivated.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deployment switches shall not be connected in parallel. 2. At least one of the deployment switches shall disconnect the negative battery terminal from the electrical ground. (FYS 2.2.2.1.1) 3. At least two of the deployment switches shall disconnect the positive battery terminal from the rest of the satellite. (FYS 2.2.2.1.3) 4. At least two of the deployment switches shall disconnect all of the positive solar cell terminals from the rest of the satellite. (FYS 2.2.2.1.4) 5. At least one of the deployment switches shall disconnect the the other satellite systems from the power busses. 6. The CubeSat shall have, at a minimum, two deployment switches, of the pusher/plunger variety, centred at the $-Z$ end face of a rail standoff (JX 2.2.1.1). 7. Deployment switch activation force shall not be greater than 3 N (NR 4.1.4.7, JX 2.2.1.5, FYS 2.2.2.9).
Notes	<p>An inhibit is considered to be a power interrupt device. A control for an inhibit (electrical or software) cannot be counted as an inhibit (NR 4.2.1.3). “Activation of the satellite” includes activation of real time clocks (RTCs). An RBF pin (or equivalent) is not considered as an inhibit.</p> <p>This requirement originates from JX 2.2.1.6, NR 4.2.1.3 and FYS 2.2.2.1.</p>

ID	FYS-EPS-11
Title	Remove-Before-Flight pin
Text	<p>An RBF pin shall be implemented. To this pin, a label with the text “Remove Before Flight” shall be attached.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Insertion of the RBF pin shall disconnect all power from all of the satellite sub systems. Ground charging of batteries shall be possible with inserted RBF pin (NR 4.2.1.3, FYS 2.2.3.2) 2. The RBF pin, when inserted, shall not protrude more than 6.5 mm from the rails. (cds[4] 3.3.7.3, FYS 2.2.3.3) 3. The RBF pin shall be placed inside the access port region of the satellite. (see green area in fig. 2.7).
Notes	This requirement originates from cds[4] 3.3.7 and FYS 2.2.3.1.

Figure 2.7.: Dimensions and position of the CubeSat access port as per CubeSat Design Specification (CDS)[4]

ID	2-EPS-1
Title	Battery Pack Capacity
Text	The battery pack shall have a minimum usable capacity $E_{bat,req}$ of 15 Wh. The term “usable capacity” refers to the amount of charge that can be taken from the battery pack, without violation of the DOD constraint.
Notes	<p>The DOD parameter will have to be determined by the developer in concordance with the minimum amount of required charging cycles.</p> <p>The capacity value demanded by this requirement is derived as follows: System requirement 9 specifies that the EDU module shall be able to be active for three continuous hours. It is assumed that the EDU module consumes 5 W. This results in an energy consumption of 15 Wh.</p>

ID	2-EPS-2
Title	Battery Pack Cycles
Text	The required battery capacity shall be available for at least 5000 charging cycles.
Notes	The DOD parameter has to be chosen according to the amount of required charging cycles. Usually, a smaller DOD means a higher count of charging cycles. This leads to the circumstance that the actual battery pack capacity will be larger than the required one.

ID	2-EPS-3
Title	EPS Dimensions
Text	The dimensions of the assembled EPS PCB stack including batteries shall not exceed a cuboid of 85 mm x 85 mm x 32 mm
Notes	-

ID	4-EPS-1
Title	Unoccupied Z faces
Text	No solar panel shall be mounted onto the Z- face of the satellite.
Notes	The antennas of the CubeSat shall be mounted on the Z- face.

ID	3-EPS-1
Title	Housekeeping Data
Text	<p>The EPS shall acquire the following data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Battery temperature in degree Celsius (°C) with a resolution of less than 1 °C. • Battery charge- and discharge rate in Milliampere (mA) with a resolution of less than 10 mA. • Battery voltage in Millivolt (mV) with a resolution of less than 10 mV. • Solar panel current in Milliampere (mA) with a resolution of less than 10 mA. • Solar panel voltage in Millivolt (mV) with a resolution of less than 10 mV.
Notes	These values are referred to as “Housekeeping data”.

ID	3-EPS-2
Title	Housekeeping Data Frequency
Text	Housekeeping data shall be acquired as current values (as opposed to average values) with a frequency of 1 Hz with an acceptable deviation of 0.1 Hz.
Notes	-

ID	3-EPS-3
Title	Housekeeping Data Historic values
Text	Only the most recent data shall be available. There shall be no storage of historical data. No timestamps shall be provided.
Notes	-

ID	3-EPS-4
Title	Housekeeping Data Interface
Text	Housekeeping data shall be made available through an interface that serves only the purpose of configuration of the data acquisition and retrieval of the data. The interface shall consist of two independent channels. The first channel shall be connected to CSBI X- pins 27 to 38. The second channel shall be connected to CSBI X+ pins 29 to 30.
Notes	-

ID	9-EPS-1
Title	Solar Cell Performance
Text	The combined mean power output over one CubeSat orbit of all solar cells shall be at least 1.5 W with a likely hood of at least 95%. A solar cell temperature of 60 °C shall be assumed.
Notes	The power budget calculation that leads to the 1.5 W requirement can be seen in Appendix A.1 . The power budget has been calculated under the assumption of a worst case orbit (i.e. 350 km altitude and a beta angle of 0°).

A. Appendix

A.1. Power Budget

STS1 Power Budget Power Budget

Power available 2,53 W
 Percent of time in Sun 60,32 % percent
 Initial Orbit Period 5482,4 sec
 Initial Orbit Period 1,52 hours

Quick Summary - Power Usage	
Day Power	1,6 W
Night Power	1,4 W
Orbit Average	1,50 W

Key:
 User Input
 Calculation result
 Constant

	Voltage	Component Power (W)	Day/Night/Both	Day Power (W)	Day Duty Cycle	Day Avg Power (W)	Night Power (W)	Night Duty Cycle	Night Avg Power (W)	Orbit Avg Power(W)	Peak Power(W)
EDU		4,52		4,52		0,38	3,72		0,37	0,38	4,52
Camera	3,3	0,80	Day	0,80	0,01	0,01	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
Raspberry Pi active	3,3	3,50	Both	3,50	0,10	0,35	3,50	0,10	0,35	0,35	
Sensors (Temp, gyro, accel,...)	3,3	0,01	Both	0,01	0,10	0,00	0,01	0,10	0,00	0,00	
GPS	3,3	0,18	Both	0,18	0,10	0,02	0,18	0,10	0,02	0,02	
Dosimeter	3,3	0,03	Both	0,03	0,10	0,00	0,03	0,10	0,00	0,00	
OBC		0,12		0,12		0,06	0,12		0,06	0,06	0,12
Processor	5	0,05	Both	0,05	1,00	0,05	0,05	1,00	0,05	0,05	
Sensors	3,3	0,01	Both	0,01	0,20	0,00	0,01	0,20	0,00	0,00	
Memory (2x FRAM, 1x Flash)	3,3	0,06	Both	0,06	0,20	0,01	0,06	0,20	0,01	0,01	
COM		6,13		6,13		0,43	6,13		0,43	0,43	6,13
S/C Receiver (Active)	2,5	0,13	Both	0,13	1,00	0,13	0,13	1,00	0,13	0,13	
S/C Transmitter (Active)	2,5	6,00	Both	6,00	0,05	0,30	6,00	0,05	0,30	0,30	
EPS		0,06		0,06		0,08	0,06		0,08	0,08	0,06
ADCs	0	0,06	Both	0,06	0,50	0,03	0,06	0,50	0,03	0,03	
Ideal Diodes	0	0,05	Both	0,05	1,00	0,05	0,05	1,00	0,05	0,05	
Total Avg Power						0,95			0,94	0,95	10,83
Power Design Margin		20 %				0,19			0,19	0,19	2,17
Subtotal Power						1,14			1,13	1,13	12,99
Charging and Conversion Losses						0,46			0,23	0,36	4,78
Battery Charging (Efficiency 95%)		0,93				0,05			0,00	0,03	1,82
Power Conversion (64%)						0,41			0,23	0,34	2,96
Power Required (W)						1,60			1,36	1,50	15,61
Power Available (W)						2,53			0,00	1,53	
Power Balance (W)						0,93			-1,36	0,03	

Bibliography

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